

RURAL DEVELOPMENT, INCLUSIVE GROWTH AND POVERTY ALLEVIATION: NIGERIAN AND INDIAN PERSPECTIVESⁱ

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Abstract:

All human societies desire growth and development especially the rural-based which are characterized by economic backwardness, the absence of basic social amenities, abject poverty and high level of illiteracy. This gap can be reduced when the people living in rural areas are incorporated in the national development plan. It is pertinent to note that any policy meant to upgrade and develop rural communities must involve agricultural and cottage industries sector as poverty Reduction measures. The gap that exists between the haves and the have-nots in the developing countries is continuously widening as a result of the absence of sound social development policies that will ensure redistribution of resources to touch members of every society. This paper discusses the comparative rural development, inclusive growth and poverty alleviation strategies of Nigeria and India. The improvement of the living standard of the rural dwellers would help to alleviate poverty without jeopardizing their rights as citizens. The paper also discussed the rural development and poverty alleviation policies of the two countries. The revelation is that India is doing well in the implementation of these policies than Nigeria. Therefore, Nigeria should learn from India regarding proper implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of such policies for the betterment of the country for other African countries to follow.

Keywords: rural development, growth, development, poverty alleviation, agriculture

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1. Introduction

The notion of rural development and inclusive growth as a panacea to the reduction of poverty in the global sphere is of paramount importance toward addressing social inequality and attaining an egalitarian society. Rural development strategies and programs in developing countries like Nigeria and India are basically similar in terms of government policies and the social and economic status of the rural poor. According to Gangopadhyay, Mukhopadhyay and Singh (2008) rural development in India is considered as the most important factor for the progress and development of the country's economy. This is because the majority of the Indian population lives in rural areas; it is estimated to cover up to 65% of the country's population. The policies for rural development in India are solely on inclusive growth and poverty alleviation. Such policies include the creation of job opportunities to the rural dwellers, provision of basic social and infrastructural facilities, social amenities in the rural areas. Similarly, Nigeria also sees rural development as a mechanism for fighting poverty at the agrarian communities (Nwachukwu & Ezeh, 2007). *"It is widely recognized that poverty, inequality, and growth are closely intertwined and form a complex set of triangular relationships"* (Liu, 2017: 1). The most significant aspect is the belief that inclusive growth can contribute to poverty alleviation. However, this can only be achieved if the implementation of growth and development programs is evenly distributed so as to reach every citizen irrespective of race or gender, in some "equitable" manner. In a society where a significant number of citizens are badly affected by absolute poverty, like Nigeria and India. Growth and development can only be inclusive and sustainable if and only if it reaches those surviving below the poverty line. CIA Book of Record in Kinnan, et al, 2011 reveal that *"between 52 and 72 per cent of Nigerians live on less than one dollar per day"*, while Tewari, (2015) said, *"more than 75% of India lives in less than 1\$ per day"*.

With the current World Bank ranking, it seems that India's poverty level has reduced in the global poverty ranking from 125 million in 2016 to 73 million. Its number one position is now being occupied by Nigeria with 83 million of those living below poverty level clearly portrayed the similarities of the two countries. This indicates that lots of efforts have to be made by the government of the two countries to rescue the situation. The paper suggests that for Nigeria to reach the promised land, it has to follow how India implements its rural development strategies, policies and programs that led to the gradual reduction of poverty level among the poor Indians. In doing so, the living standard of the Nigerian rural dwellers will improve and the poverty will reduce to the minimal.

This paper covers the introduction, conceptual definitions, some post-independence rural development policies sphere headed by the two countries. Additionally, discussed on inclusive growth and poverty alleviation programs, and the challenges encountered from the implementation of these programs, and finally, the conclusion is drawn.

2. Rural Development in Nigeria and India

The term rural development has different dimensions. It means different things to different people; each author tries to define it according to his educational background (Mayowa & Iyanda, 2014). In a nutshell, the concept of Rural Development is multi-dimensional. According to Panda and Majumba Rural Development “generally refers to the process of improving the quality of life and economic well-being of people living in relatively isolated and sparsely populated areas” (Panda & Majumda, 2013). Rural Development can also be defined as “the integrated approach to food production as well as physical, social and institutional infrastructural provisions with an ultimate goal of bringing about both quantitative and qualitative changes which result in an improved living standard of the rural population” (Mayowa & Iyanda, 2014: 3). The United Nations Agency for Social and Economic Development defines rural development as “the quantitative change or upliftment in the standard of people in the rural areas, brought about through an integrated approach, by both government and non-governmental agencies and the people themselves”.

Janvry (2005) argues that the issues concerning Rural Development are not been considered worthy or something very serious by the global agencies. He further stressed that going by the statistical and demographic data which reveals 75% of the world poverty is in rural areas. Unfortunately, only 25% of the international donor agencies and philanthropic organizations “leading portfolios goes to rural areas”. Rural areas also suffer from social exclusion when compared to the urban areas in all Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) ramifications. It is clear that rural populace suffered in the areas of education, gender issues, infant and child mortality, maternal health and mortality. Others are communicable and chronic illnesses and issues related to environmental degradations and pollution. Those international development partners that that contributes to poverty alleviation programs in rural areas have “directed their money to welfare transfers” instead of improving the income level of rural dwellers, which appears more costly and more demanding. However, the present Sustainable Development Goals SDGs introduced by the UN seems to address these problems in the outlined 17 points adopted by the policy which emphasized on poverty reduction as the first priority (UNDP, 2018).

3. Strategist for the Implementation of Rural Development Policies in Nigeria: An Overview

Rural development in Nigeria started since the British colonial administration, which was the pre-independence era when Township ordinance was promulgated in 1917. The ordinance classified Nigeria in two-three classes the 1st, 2nd, and the 3rd; the first class is the one with the concentration of rural infrastructures. This may be due to selfish colonialist interest and for easy access to the agricultural products produced in rural communities. Railway lines were constructed and linked to various locations for easy conveyance of cocoa, rubber, groundnut, cotton etc. After the country’s independence,

Rural Development became inevitable in Nigeria for the fact that more than half of the country's population lives in rural areas. According to the National Population Commission in Shehu (2018), 52.7 per cent of Nigeria's population resides in rural areas. He further stated that in spite the fact that these rural dwellers are small-scale farmers which cultivate land at peasant level, hardly cultivate one hectare of farmland "*per household must of which are arable crops*". Their farm produces constitute a significant percentage of the food Nigeria consumed. Going by this statement, it is unfair for any country to sideline such category of people in as much as peace and security is the priority of that country.

Nigeria like other developing countries made so many efforts to integrate rural communities into the life of the nation by putting them on the course of development but could not achieve this mission. Over the years "*Conditions have continued to worsen and poverty has become a major issue in the rural areas in spite of their potentials*" (Olaranti & Olayiwola, 2005). In its effort to improve the lives of rural people, the Nigerian government formed many programs for developing and upgrade rural communities. The first effort appears in the Third National Development Plan NDP (1975-80) which put much emphasis on egalitarianism in order to achieve national integration and unity through the adoption of integrated rural development policies and programs. However, the comprehensive rural development strategy appears in the Fourth National Development Plan, 1981-1985. This plan prioritized on rural development, to justify this, the government "*emphasized among other things the need for the balanced development of the different sectors of the economy and of the various geographic areas of the country*". It also stressed the need to provide rural areas with basic infrastructural facilities, by doing so the living standard of the rural dwellers will improve (Egbe, 2014). It is due to these reasons many rural development policies and strategist were formulated and implemented within the plan period as shown below even though Egbe (2014) claims that the programs recorded little success.

3.1 The National Accelerated Food Production Project (NAFPP)

This program started prior to the implementation of the third NDP. It was promulgated in 1973 by the then Military regime of General Yakubu Gowon and it continued up until 1976 when it was reviewed by the Murtala Obasanjo regime and changed to Operation Feed the Nation Program. This was an agricultural and rural development policy specifically meant to enhance food production in "*specific areas and sub-sectors of the agricultural economy. NAFPP relied heavily on the cooperative approach as well as on technical assistance for its success. The scheme was a well-conceived and guided change program for rural development, especially in the area of food production*" (Olaranti & Olayiwola, 2005).

3.2 The Agricultural Development Programs (ADPs)

The Agricultural Development Programs was established in 1975. It was piloted with three enclaves and later on spread to the other parts of the country. ADPs were initiated specifically to increase food cultivation and production in order to generate incomes to

the rural farmers. To achieve these, the following characteristics were outlined: 1. *“an input and credit supply system through a network of farm service centers which ensure that no farmer travels more than 5-15km to purchase needed farm inputs”*; 2. provision of many *“feeder road network”* that will give more chance for the farmers to cultivate new lands and doing so would boost food supply and other farm produce and timely supply of inputs, 3. *“joint state-federal collaboration for project implementation;”* and 4) *“solid project management together with built-in project monitoring and evaluation”*. These programs symbolize a new strategy to *“agricultural and rural development both in their integrated supply of farm inputs and infrastructural support and in their efforts to revamp and revitalize extension services”* (Olaranti & Olayiwola, 2005).

3.3 The River Basin Development Authorities

This is an innovation by the Nigerian government to ensure the inclusivity of the rural populace and improve their income level. It is done through diversification of rural food production and a sound rural development program (Olaranti & Olayiwola, 2005). The government in 1977 initiated and creates eleven River Basin Development Authorities. The program was meant to bust agricultural production through both irrigation and wet season farming to increase food production and provide rural areas with basic and necessary infrastructures were established to undertake food production and the provision of rural infrastructure. During the implementation stage of this program, many DAMS and irrigation schemes were constructed and farmers were provided with fertilizer and other improve crop varieties at an affordable rate.

3.4 The Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme

In order to ensure the realization of the River Basin Development Program, the government in 1977, initiated the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund Decree. The objective of the program was *“to provide cover in respect of loans granted for agricultural purposes was promulgated”*. Having the government baking would encourage the commercial banks to provide loans to the local farmers and the commercial farmers who engage in large-scale farming. The program is formed to benefit both the commercial, small-scale and literate farmers.

3.5 The Directorate of Food, Roads and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI)

Subsequent to the adoption and implementation of the structural adjustment program (SAP), the then Nigerian government created Directorate of Food, Roads and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI) in 1986. It was an integrated approach to rural development (Hussaini, 2014). This newly introduced program DFRRI was specifically meant as a panacea of promoting developmental projects at local or rural areas. Its main concern is *“on the provision of water and the construction, rehabilitation and maintenance of an effective rural feeder road network”*. DFRRI had the following objectives: i). to promote a framework for grassroots social mobilization. b). to mount a virile program of development, monitoring, and performance evaluation. c). to provide rural areas with

access roads and potable water. d). to improve rural sanitation, literacy, and technology (Olaranti & Olayiwola, 2005).

3.6 National Directorate of Employment (NDE)

This Directorate was established in 1986 in order to encourage self-employment and self-reliance instead of salary employment. It was designed to provide more employment to the Nigerian poor with special attention to the teeming youth through skill acquisition and entrepreneurship development. The loan-provision system was initiated with the aim of accelerating entrepreneurship development (Inedu, 2016). The Directorate initiated the plan and outlined and implements four important essential programs. These are Vocational Skills Development Program (VSDP), Special Public Works (SPW), Small Scale Enterprises (SSE) and Rural Employment Promotion Program (RPP) (Isa & Timothy, 2014).

3.7 Better Life Program (BLP)

This program came into being a year after the implementation of the structural adjustment program (SAP) in 1987. It was initiated by the wife of the Military President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria in order to improve the lives of rural women by enhancing their income level. It was part of the rural development strategies of the then administration of bringing development to the rural areas. According to Oyeranti and Olayiwola (2005) the BLP main objectives are:

- a) The desire to stimulate and motivate women in rural areas towards achieving a better and higher standard of living, as well as sensitize the general populace to the plight of rural women;
- b) Educate women on simple hygiene, family planning, the importance of childcare and to increase literacy;
- c) To mobilize women for concrete activities towards achieving specific objectives, including seeking leadership roles in all spheres of national life; and
- d) To raise the social consciousness of women about their rights, as well as social, political and economic responsibilities.

Subsequent to the implementation of the program, the scope of the program was extended to cover not only rural women but also urban women and cooperative societies. It reduced gender restriction, in other word, men appear to be members through cooperatives and therefore the name was changed to *“from Better Life Program for Rural Women to Better Life Program (BLP)”*. This new development entails that the program now covered several areas *“relate to enhancing labour productivity and entrepreneurship development. Areas covered include health, agriculture, education, social welfare, and cooperatives”*. The establishment of cooperative societies in the policy program was meant to enhance entrepreneurship development. These led to the establishment of several cooperative societies such as: *“fishing, farming, marketing, and weaving”* and a variety of crafts in order to achieve the objectives. The cooperatives were linked with the Peoples Bank for easy access to loans to the targeted groups.

Additionally, a linkage was “*created between the two agencies*”. Few years Nigeria witnessed changes of governments and these led to the restructuring the program and narrow down its activities. It was later called Family Support Program (FSP) with special attention on hygiene and other health components (Mayowa & Iyanda, 2014).

3.8 The National Agricultural Land Development Authority (NALDA)

This is another giant stride by the Federal government of Nigeria. It was meant to bust agricultural cultivation and production through a scheme, to use the abundant virgin land which is grossly underutilized. The federal government in 1991 established the National Agricultural Land Development Authority (NALDA). The aim of such initiative is to overcome the problem of food production through enlargement of the sizes of the farms and support the farmers with necessary inputs so as to enhance productivity as part of the program objective. This will go a long way in integrating them, and in turn, would alleviate rural poverty. The agency was shouldered with the responsibility to clear, prepare 30,000 to 50,000 hectares of land in all states of the Federation between the period of 1992 to 1994. NALDA was to also develop a strategy to ensure the formation of farm settlements in order to accommodate at least 7,500-12,500 small-scale farmers in the area developed “*such that each participating farmer lives within a 3km-5km radius of his farmland*”.

4. Strategies for Implementation of Rural Development Programs in India

Rural development in India existed since time immemorial. However, giant efforts similar to what the country called rural development nowadays were made only in the 19th century just like that of Nigeria. India considers rural development among her top priorities after the country gain independence the “Objectives in this regard were spelt out in The Directive Principles of State Policy in Part IV of the Constitution”. Lalith (2004) claims that the fundamental objectives of the rural development program in India are poverty alleviation, inclusive growth and creation of employment opportunities. The objectives would be achieved through the provision of infrastructural and improvement of economic activities, skill acquisition, entrepreneurship development and vocational training to the teeming jobless youth. By so doing would provide job opportunities to “marginalize farmers/ labourers” in order to reduce rural-urban migration. Even though India, tries to combine both rural and urban economy into the national economy, but the development of rural communities is paramount. This is for the fact that two third of the Indian population is badly affected with poverty and those who leave below the poverty line are residing in that rural communities. The development strategies in India are clearly outlined in the National Rural Development Employment Act of 2005 as stated in India’s post-independent National Development Plans.

4.1. Community Development Program

This was the first organized effort or the pioneer program Indian government made for the purpose of developing rural areas. The program when implemented will create employment opportunities among the rural populace and provide basic infrastructural facilities on areas such as health, education, roads, telecommunication among others. This is in order to integrate them into the life of the nation and participate fully in the nation's progress and development. The program came into being on 2nd October 1952; from there, India experienced a turning point on rural development (Agrawal, 2014).

4.2. Food for Work Program (FWP)

This program was created and implemented by the then Janata government in 1977. The major objective of the program was the provision of employment opportunities to the jobless, "unemployed/underemployed" rural dwellers during the "slack season. The wages paid to the workers were in kind, i.e., food grains".

4.3 Integrated Rural Development Program (IRDP)

The Indian Integrated Rural Development Program was launched in 1978. The major aim of the program is providing support to the poverty affected groups who mostly reside in rural areas. It provides subsidized form of banks loan "for productive employment opportunities through successive plan periods". later, other rural supports plans among which includes "training of Rural Youths for Self-Employment (TRYSE), Development of Women and Children in Rural Areas (DWCRA), Supply of Improved Tool Kits to Rural Artisans (SITRA)", and many more related initiatives and programs where implemented. They are meant to improve and upgrade the lives of the rural dwellers in India (Sharma, 1980).

4.4 Rural Housing (Indira Awaas Yojana)

The National Housing policy is created by the Indian government to provide "Housing for All" Indians as one of the essential needs for the survival of every human being. Therefore, provision of affordable houses was incorporated as part of the priority areas "under the National Rural Employment Program which began in 1980". In order to achieve this policy, the Indian government in 1998 promulgated National Housing and Habitat policy which aims to address the providing shelter for accommodation problem.

4.5 SwarJayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana (SGSY)

This is a comprehensive self-employment policy meant for the rural poor. It was initiated and implemented by the Indian government in April 1999; it is the single self-employment program for the rural poor. It is categorized as the comprehensive program because of its scope which covers every side of "self-employment". This includes classifying of "rural poor into Self Help Groups (SHGs) and their capacity building, training, planning of activity clusters, infrastructure development, financial assistance through bank credit and subsidy and marketing support" (Agrawal, 2014) among others.

4.6 Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojana (PMGSY)

This program is meant to bring development to the rural areas through the construction of well-connected road networks. Indian government believed that rural roads network are essential for the economic growth and poverty reduction in rural communities. The road connectivity is to cover hard to reach rural villages. According to National Rural Roads Development Agency, (2000) while piloting the program in 2000, *“Government has launched a 100% Centrally Sponsored Scheme called the Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojana”*. During the program, all rural communities with the population of 500 persons and above living in a flat land and over 250 in hilly areas are proposed to be connected with *“all-weather”* tar-roads by the end of the Tenth Plan Period”. By the last quarter of 2017, the program has recorded a success story of covering 82%. Going by the progress report, the remaining 47,000 communities are supposed to be completed by the first quarter of 2019 (The Economic Time, 2017, Dec, 16).

4.7 Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA)

MGNREGA come into being after at list 5 decades of India’s stride to improving the living standard of the rural dwellers through various rural development strategies and programs. The initiative is perceived as a milestone for poverty alleviation as well as a vehicle for providing employment opportunities among Indian rural populace through labour force generation in rural areas. The program was popularly known as *“Silver Bullet”* for rural poverty eradication and creation of more employment opportunities. MGNREGA 2005 *“guarantees 100 days of employment in a financial year to any rural household whose adult members are willing to do unskilled manual work”*. The act was put to work in 2006 with 200 districts as a piloted test and subsequent 2 the year 2008 the program was extended to the entire rural districts of India (Ganiee, 2014, Panda & Majumda, 2013).

5. The Challenges of Rural Development Program Implementation in Nigeria and India

Despite efforts made by Nigerian and Indian governments to improve the lives of the rural populace through various rural development strategies and policies and spending huge amount of human and material resources, still, these countries are facing some challenges. Specifically, in Nigeria, one of the serious problem affecting agriculture and rural development program is desertification and Flood disaster. This cause a serious setback to crop production to some extent hampered and delay the implementation of government programs and policies in Nigeria. Secondly, the protracted conflict that existed between the farmers and hidere for many years causes serious unrest among the two communities and hinders the implementation of rural development programs in the country, especially in the Northern regions. Another problem is rural-urban migration. A lot of able youth migrated to urban areas in search of greener pasture. Another factor is the absence or less commitment of government when it comes to the

policy implementation and serious corruption in all governments sectors. India also faced with some problems such as erratic rainfall in some states which suffered from environmental degradation. Such states like; Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh, and Rajasthan suffers from this uncertain and inconsistency rainy season and rainfall. Other environmental problems like, “contaminated groundwater and poor soil conditions” sometimes led to other natural disasters. Most of the Indian religious and traditional/cultural practices and belief systems negatively affected rural development policies and programs. It is not only agricultural programs that is affected, but also have impacted the per-capita real income of the rural dwellers of both Nigeria and India’s citizens. Other factors include illiteracy, the high illiteracy rate among rural dwellers of both two countries create great problem toward the realization of most of the rural development policies. This is because, the people whose policies and programs are meant for and who are to benefit from are illiterate (Nwagboso & Duke, 2012).

6. Conceptual Clarifications

6.1. Poverty

According to Ponmuthusaravanan and Ravi (2014):

“Poverty has been defined in income or expenditure terms and measured in absolute or in relative terms. Absolute poverty refers to a set standard which is consistent over time and between countries. On the other hand, relative poverty is the condition of having fewer resources or less income than others within a society or country or compared to worldwide averages. Relative poverty views poverty as socially defined and dependent on social context. Hence, relative poverty is a measure of income inequality.”

According to IFAD (2007) cited in Adigun, Bamiro, and Adedeji (2015), the poverty rate and its spread in Nigeria seems to spread equally across the country. However, it varies from one geopolitical zone to another. Some zones are badly affected than others for instance; the northern states who shares boundary with France speaking countries of Niger and Chad have more poverty then others especially in their rural communities then urban. These areas suffer a lack of basic social service and infrastructural facilities necessary for the survival of every society or community. The facilities are either limited or completely absent. While on the other hand, the Indian scenario according to World Bank (2018) poverty is severe in Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Jharkhand, Madhya Pradesh, Orissa, Rajasthan, and Uttar Pradesh states than other parts of India.

6.2. Inclusive Growth and Poverty Alleviation

The concepts of rural development, inclusive growth and poverty alleviation are intertwined and interwoven; in another word, they are inseparable. Whenever someone

talks about rural development, it means he is talking about a reduction of the poverty level. And rural poverty can only be alleviated when the inhabitant of the said area are allowed to participate in the developmental process.

Inclusive growth, while requiring poverty reduction, is a broader concept. It focuses on reducing inequalities and different forms of discrimination. Furthermore, it also includes widespread exclusion and unequal access to growth's benefits for women and girls, persons with disabilities, ethnic/linguistic minority groups and entire regions and countries. Inclusive growth also requires full respect for human rights (Lavopa & Szirmai, 2012).

6.3 Inclusive Growth

Inclusive growth means socio-economic growth where people have carried along in the distribution of social services, a wealth of the nation, health care delivery service and so on. The growth can only be inclusive when it reduces poverty and poverty can only be reduced when inequality and discrimination on the basis of race or religion and tradition are addressed. This scenario is opposite to social exclusion.

The concept of inclusive growth is today recognized and adopted by the third world nations as the "key economic goal for developing countries". Their definition varies from one person to another; there is variations in its definition and classification. Birdsall (2007) outline what he perceived include the concepts and approaches to inclusive growth:

"Inclusive growth includes but extends pro-poor growth; it involves 'increasing the size and economic strata of the middle class'. The assumption is that growth which is beneficial for the large majority of people in developing countries is more likely to be economically and politically sustainable" (Birdsall, 2007).

Inclusive growth involves a long-term perspective. It focuses on the generation of productive employment, instead of direct income redistribution, in order to increase the incomes for all segments of society, particularly for the poor'.

6.4 Social Exclusion

The term Social exclusion is a new concept in the field of social determinants of health, wealth and other social indicators. Its "conceptual roots" was in Europe and the UK, in their views, Shaw, Dorling, and Smith (1999: 222) ".....'Social exclusion' refers not only to the economic hardship or relative economic poverty but also incorporates the notion of the process of marginalization – how individuals come, through their lives, to be excluded and marginalized from various aspects of social and community life".

According to White (1998) social exclusion emerge from four basic processes: (1) legal constraints or regulation that limit participation in civil society (e.g. when citizenship is denied for certain groups of migrants and their dependents, even if they are born in the country, as is the case in Germany for instance). (2) lack of certain goods

or social services that limit full participation in society (e.g. adapted facilities for the disabled). (3) exclusion from social production (e.g. labeling of certain groups as undesirable). (4) economic exclusion from average consumption (e.g. through relative or absolute poverty).

Shaw et al. (1999) stress that, those individuals and groups affected from social exclusion vary from culture to culture country to country and from society to society, but it seems some are more affected than others.

6.5 Inclusive Growth and Poverty in Nigeria

Bello, et al. (2009) reveals that the level of poverty in Nigeria during the period of countries independence and a decade after that is from the 1960s to 1970s is very low. This may be attributed to the “steady growth in per capita real income” because the number of jobless people as at that time is minimal. Most of Nigerian engaged in agricultural works, some work in the manufacturing industries, while others work in public sectors. 1970 is said to be the year of economic misfortune, it was the period Nigeria experienced “beginning of real poverty” in the country. The period between the last quarter of the 1970s to early 1980s, when oil prices, the major source of Nigeria’s revenue started declining in 1982 and “per capita income and private consumption dropped”. Since then, according to Nnadi et al. (2013) “Nigeria witnessed continues increase in poverty level, for instance, the poverty level stood at 43% between 1985 and 1986 but rose to 54%, 61% and 66% in 1996, 1997 and 1999 respectively” (World Bank, 1995; CBN 2003 in Bello et al.,2009). The National Bureau of Statistics reported that the nation’s poverty level has to drop down to 54.4%, in 2004. Unfortunately, it rose up to 69% in 2010 and steadily increasing to 71.5% in 2011 (Okonkwo, 2015).

Figure 1: Ranking of people living with extreme poverty or below the poverty line of 10 countries of the world in from 1990 to 2013

Figure 1 shows the ranking of people living with extreme poverty or below the poverty line of 10 countries of the world in from 1990 to 2013. This indicates that after 2 decades both countries have done well toward poverty reduction in their countries. India’s

people living below the poverty line in 1990 were 338 but reduced to 218. This indicate that India has succeeded in reducing the number of poor people with 120 million people within 23 years. On the other hand, Nigeria’s condition has worsened within this period. It appears to have an increasing number of those living below poverty line with 35 million people. Moreover, this indicates that all countries have strived to reduce the menace of poverty. Among the 10 selected countries, only Nigeria is lagging behind. Poverty line can be defined as the amount of money needed for a person to meet his basic needs. It is defined as the money value of the goods and services needed to provide basic welfare to an individual. Some 70 per cent of the population and labour force in these countries ‘Nigeria and India’ still depend on agriculture for employment and income.... (Abubakar, 2018)

Table 2: Relative poverty, Non –poor, Moderate poor and extremely poor (%) 1980-2010

Year	Non-Poor	Moderate poor	Extremely poor
1980	72.8	21.0	6.2
1985	53.7	34.2	12.1
1992	57.3	28.9	13,9
1996	34.4	36.3	29.3
2004	43.3	32.4	22.0
2010	31.0	30.3	38.7

Source: NBS Harmonized Nigerian Living Standard Survey, 2010.

Table 2 above shows that 72.8 per cent of the Nigerians are doing fine in 180. They were not poor, but 27.2 per cent were poor that is when divided by 21.0 per cent as moderate poor and 6.2 per cent extremely poor. This shows that significant number of the people is poor but not extremely poor. Looking into this figure one can say that, the reason behind their good living is because farming was considered as the major source of livelihood and a business then. Later the percentage of poor has increased and superseded the non – poor in 1996. The percentage of non-poor drops down to 34.4 per cent whereas that of poor rises up to 65.6 per cent. Even then, the condition did not deteriorate until 2010 where the extremely poor superseded moderate poor with 38.7 per cent and 30.3 per cent respectively.

Table 3: Table of Poverty Rate in Nigeria (2000-2018)

Year	Population	Poverty Incident %
2000	115.2	70.10
2001	118.8	NA
2002	122.4	NA
2003	126.2	NA
2004	299.9	54.7
2005	135.5	54.7
2006	140.0	54.0
2007	140.0	54.0
2008	150.4	NA
2009	154.4	54.0

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2010	158.6	69.9
2011	162.9	71.5
2012	167.3	72.0
2013	171.8	NA
2014	176.5	NA
2015	181.2	NA
2016	185.9	NA
2017	190.9	NA
2018	197.3	93.9

Source: Oriola (2009); CBN (2013) NA = Not available, in Abubakar et al, 2018.

Table 3 shows the estimated number of Nigerian poverty rate from 2000-2018. In the year 2000, the estimated population as at then was 115.2 in which 70.10 per cent are poor. While in 2018 both the estimated population and poverty rate have raised to 197.3 million out of which 93.9 per cent are poor which is equivalent to 86.9 million extremely poor people. This appears to be the highest figure worldwide and with this number, Nigeria has taken the unwanted position of India as number one country with the highest number of poor inhabitants in the world. India occupies the 2nd position and democratic republic of Congo the third position respectively.

The above chart shows the rapid population growth in Nigeria from 150 million people in 2008 to over 190 million in 2017. As the population is increasing so also the economy, but the poverty level is increasing which is quite contrary to India. In the case of India, as their population is increasing, the economy is also increasing and the level of poverty is decreasing annually.

Table 4: The Rural and Urban Poverty rate base on the Estimate Population 1980-2010

Year	Rural Poverty (%)	Urban Poverty (%)	Estimated Population (Millions)	The proportion of Population in Nigeria
1980	28.1	17.2	65	27.2
1985	46.3	37.8	75	46.3
1992	42.7	37.5	91.5	42.8
1996	65.6	58.2	120	62.2
2000	65.65	58.6	120	62.2

Source: Okuneye, et al., 2004 in Abubakar et al 2018

Table 4 above shows extends of poverty level among the rural and urban poor in Nigeria. Rural areas recorded the highest number of people affected by Poverty than Urban communities. In 1980, the country's rural poverty level was 28.1 per cent and urban poverty was 17.2 per cent also 27.2 per cent of the country's population was poor in 1980. *"Both the rural and urban poverty increased to 65.65% and 58.6% respectively in the year 2000"*.

With all the above development, misfortune and similar instance related to the endemic nature of poverty affecting Nigeria makes it difficult to achieve the Millennium development goal target. Additionally, the country is classified among the poorest country in the world. Nigerian government became worried about the alarming rate of poverty bedeviling the country. From the year 1999 to 2016 government has made a giant stride toward alleviating the countries poverty. This led to the emergence of Poverty Alleviation program (PAP) in the year 2000 and subsequently changed to National Poverty Eradication Program (NAPEP). The National Poverty Eradication Program (NAPEP) was introduced in 2001 in order to arrest the increasing poverty level among Nigerians (Edeh, Michael, & Kenneth, 2017, Hussaini, 2014).

6.6 Inclusive Growth and Poverty Alleviation in India

When India got independent, the country survived under traditional and agrarian economy, extremely poor communication, and transport system. Culture and tradition contributed to the clear dichotomy of social class and rigidity in social mobility. In order to address these backward inherited problems and to reduce exclusiveness and poverty level among Indians especially those who reside at the country-side. Goyal (2015) outlined the five interconnected and interdependent essentials of inclusive growth initiated by the Indian government, and these are: *"1. Poverty Reduction and increase in quantity and quality of employment 2. Agricultural Development 3. Social-Sector Development 4. Poor quality delivery systems 5. Social indicators are much lower for scheduled castes and scheduled tribes. India like other developing nation made development plans which cater for inclusive growth."* These five years plans were meant to tackle the flowing problem so as to have a smoothly incorporate the rural poor and marginalized to the life of the nation to enable them to contribute fully to the country's progress.

Goyal (2015) claims that the Poorer and marginalized segment of the country such as *"the Scheduled Castes (SCs), Scheduled Tribes (STs) and minorities"* did not benefit from economic Growth of their country. Low Human Development is at extreme

because the indicators such as education, maternal health, and infant mortality and literacy level are very high when compared to the global standard. Furthermore, there is little or no availability of essential social services necessary for the survival of people. He further elucidated the challenges facing the inclusive growth which needs to address squarely such as addressing the problem of unemployment, alleviating poverty level among rural poor, “equality of opportunity to all with freedom and dignity, and without social and political obstacles” would make India great. Others include empowerment of the marginalized and segregated groups, gender equity among others for the “growth inclusive”.

It recognized that, for the past fifty years of Indian economic development, there still exist inequitable distributions of growth among the citizen. The poorer and segregated of these people are sidelined in the policies meant to upgrade the living standard of the Indians. They hardly get integrated into the planning and implementation process. They were abandoned at the mercy God (Goyal, 2015). According to data released by the Socio-Economic Caste Census (SECC) survey cited in Tewari (2015), more than 70 million rural families suffer exclusion in one way or the other. They are excluded either from assets or socio-economic benefits. Similarly, 69 per cent of the inhabitants which is equivalent to 833 million Indians live in rural communities. Unlike Nigeria that has other programs meant for poverty reduction in addition to these rural development programs, Indian rural development programs are the same programs meant to develop rural areas and to eradicate poverty at the rural communities.

The above chart shows the level of poverty in India for almost two decades from 1993 to 2011. The figure shows that even though the Indian population is rapidly increasing on annual basis, but the poverty level seems to be gradually declining. According to the National Planning commission, the poverty level has declined from 37.2 % in 2004-2005 to 22% in 2011-2012.

6.7 Poverty in retreat in India

Nigeria recently eclipsed India as the country where the largest numbers of people are living in extreme poverty. The gap is said to be gradually widening on a daily basis as shown in the figure below.

Source: World Poverty Clock

The above chart shows the poverty level (those living below the poverty line less than \$1.90 a day) of the three countries which have the highest number of extremely poor. The countries are Nigeria, India and Democratic Republic of Congo occupying the 1st, 2nd and the 3rd positions. The report shows a remarkable decline in poverty level in India which has only 5 per cent of its 1.3 billion populations who are extremely poor while Nigeria is having 44 per cent of its 198 million populations who are extremely poor.

6.8 The Challenges of Inclusive and Poverty Alleviation Programs Implementation in Nigeria and India

Several poverty alleviation programs were initiated and implemented by the two countries to reduce the poverty level of the poor who mostly dwelled in rural areas for decades. While India recorded success in reducing its country's poverty and remarkably succeeded in the improvement of basic social indicator (UNDP, India, 2011) Nigeria achieves either little or no success. Taiwo and Agwu (2016) claim that *"instead of reducing the incidence of poverty, which is the country's sole aim, these programs tend to serve as means for draining the national resources due to the pursuit of parochial interests, as a result fostering corruption and dishonesty"*. They further stated that serious measures need to be taken by the government to tackle mismanagement and lack of accountability among the top management of the implementation agencies. It is rather unfortunate to say that a country which occupied the first position in terms of economic growth and development in the whole Sub-Saharan Africa. At the same time to occupy the first position among the countries with the highest number of poor in the world. Some of the

challenges of poverty reduction program according to Hassan et al (2012) are Policy inconsistency, Political Instability and lack of continuity of government programs. Many programs meant to alleviate poverty are “jettison” whenever the country experienced change of government. The successive government always does away with every policy or program initiated by the previous government and establishes a new one that will be categorized as their initiative and not the initiative of the past government. For instance, the case with Operation Feed the Nation, Green Revolution and Better Life for Rural Women to mention but a few. Another challenge is Insecurity in the country. This seriously contributes to the increase in poverty level among Nigerians. The Northern region especially the North Eastern zone is terribly hampered by the Boko Haram insurgency. The uprising makes a lot of people displaced from their homes and business activities especially the rural people whose primary occupation is farming were forced to abandon it. Other related insecurity problems include; ethnic and religious crises, Arm Banditry and Cattle rustling (Shehu, 2018). No wonder the World Bank poverty ranking categorized North Eastern Nigeria as the region badly heated by poverty. In 2010, Nigeria’s poverty level raised to 84%, North East 69.0% with Bornu State occupying the first position (Tela, 2014). Turning to Indian, even though India is steadily declining in poverty level as well as the basic social indicators as mentioned above. There are still some challenges which need to be tackled by both the Indian government and the NGOs. There is still a bunch of Indian whom were badly affected with poverty in seven states outlined by the UNDP report as home to India’s poorest. According to the report, the states constitute 64 per cent of citizens living below the poverty line in the country. The states are: “*Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Jharkhand, Madhya Pradesh, Orissa, Rajasthan, and Uttar Pradesh*”. Other challenges India need to overcome are the condition of “*people belonging to Scheduled Castes (SCs) and Scheduled Tribes (STs)*”. The poverty levels of this groups seems to be highest in the country, they are said to cover 50 per cent of poor and underprivileged families of the country.

7. Conclusion

Both Nigeria and Indians development were urban-centered. This means the development in these countries were urban bias they tend to develop Urban Area at the detriment of rural areas. That was why National development plans of both the two countries were promulgated to address these issues. In Nigeria, the subsequent three development plans, the first, the second and the third showed less concerned on rural development. Only the fourth national plan covers rural development as its priority. In India, the problems appear similar because prior to the development plans little attention was shown to the rural dwelling population. Even though they constitute the highest number of the countries inhabitants. However, some of the policies and programs recorded success in India more than Nigeria. The inclusive growth and poverty alleviation of both countries go hand in hand, they are interwoven. Only when people have been carried alone in the development programs in their domain, their

condition will improve and their poverty level will reduce. The poverty level in India among the Scheduled Caste and Scheduled Tribe is at its pick. In Nigeria those people living in the hard-to-reach areas also were excluded in the country's development in all ramifications. They lack pipe born water, health care delivery services, roads, electricity schools to mention but a few. The World Poverty Clock report, compiled by Brookings Institute July 2018 ranked Nigeria as the country with the highest number of people affected with poverty with 87 million people living below the poverty line. While India's position is improving, it raised to the second position with 75.9 million people as against the former. The limitation of this research is that, the research covers rural development and poverty alleviation program in the post-independence era, any initiatives or program/policies adopted by the British colonial administration been the sole colonial master for both Nigeria and India were not discussed and elaborated. The findings of this research revealed that India is gradually catching up in the program of rural development, inclusiveness and poverty alleviation strategists and policies. It has continued to gradually yield a positive outcome. Hence, more efforts shall put in place to improve the conditions of the schedule Cast and Schedule Tribes. In India these group are the segregated and disadvantaged people even though they constitute the significant number of poor in the country. Unfortunately, the Nigeria's situation is worsening due to so many reasons. These include, lack of continuity, corruption ethnic-religious crises, and Insecurity due to Boko Haram Insurgency and Arm Banditry/ Cattle thefts in the areas that are badly affected by poverty among other things. With the recent revelation of poverty in Nigeria and Africa, Nigeria is the country with the highest population and the country with the largest economy in Africa. The paper suggested that, Nigeria shall copy and adopt India's Rural Development and poverty alleviation strategists for other African countries to follow.

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